

From Intra Site to Macro Scale GIS analysis. The work of the AeGIS Lab

Vassilis Evangelidis

Institute of Language and Speech Processing
Athena Research Center
vevangelidis@athenarc.gr

Yiannis Mourthos

Institute of Language and Speech Processing
Athena Research Center
jmourthos@athenarc.gr

Melpomeni Karta

Institute of Language and Speech Processing
Athena Research Center
melpomek@athenarc.gr

Introduction: The AeGIS Laboratory's Quest from Intra-Site to Macro Scale GIS

The AeGIS Laboratory (<http://aegis.athenarc.gr/>), established by the Athena Research Center in Xanthi, stands as a reflection of the enduring commitment of the Center to the realm of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) technology, dating back to 2002.¹ This commitment has revolved around the application of GIS techniques in recording and analyzing archaeological data. By employing an array of methods including mapping, geospatial databases, photogrammetry, and archaeometry, the laboratory endeavors to equip archaeologists, historians, and cultural heritage practitioners with GIS tools for the high-resolution documentation and meticulous mapping analysis of archaeological sites and landscapes. It seeks to underscore the immense potential of GIS in addressing specific archaeological challenges by pioneering novel approaches, and to serve as a valuable resource and model for other institutions in Greece by demonstrating the transformative potential of GIS in addressing these challenges, offering a blueprint for integrating advanced digital processes in similar contexts.

The scope of the AeGIS Laboratory's work spans from intra-site analyses (excavation sites) to macro-scale investigations (landscape studies). Its vision extends to the integration of GIS data with game engines, marking a bold step toward immersive, three-dimensional archaeological exploration. In this paper, we delve not only into the presentation of ongoing research projects but also into the theoretical underpinnings of GIS applications. We do so from the perspective of archaeologists who use digital processes to organize and ultimately better understand their material and the questions it raises. This paper provides an overview of the AeGIS Lab's journey and contributions in the field of GIS-based archaeological research up to the present.

Intra site analysis: data handling and organization at the excavation of Karabournaki Thessaloniki

In the realm of archaeological excavations, one finds a domain where the utility of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) becomes strikingly evident.² This significance is underscored by the

¹ Tsiafaki and Evangelidis 2006; Tsionas *et al.* 2009.

² Wheatley and Gillings 2003; Neubauer 2004; Levy and Smith 2007.

intricate nature of archaeological fieldwork, where the generation, organization, and analysis of complex spatial data pose constant challenges. From the earliest stages of GIS adoption,³ particularly in countries such as the United Kingdom, the United States, and the Netherlands, field archaeologists recognized the immense potential of GIS tools in addressing these challenges. GIS facilitated the systematic management of findings, helped decipher correlations in the spatial distribution of artifacts, and enabled in-depth analyses of individual objects.⁴

In this context, GIS emerged as an innovation, enabling archaeologists to navigate the labyrinth of data accumulated during excavations.⁵ It not only streamlines the organization of spatial information, but also serves as a potent instrument for unveiling hidden insights within archaeological landscapes. This multifaceted approach, where GIS intersects with the study of each artifact and the broader archaeological context, has forever changed the way we conduct archeology.⁶

This is precisely how we have harnessed GIS tools during the archaeological excavation of Karabournaki, an archaeological site located in the Thermaic Gulf, currently investigated by the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki. The ancient settlement, which is identified by researchers as the harbour of ancient Thermi, functioned as a port from the late Archaic to -at least- the Classical and Hellenistic era and presents a variety of archaeological data and excavation finds.⁷ The areas of archaeological interest include a *toumba* (hill), a *trapeza* (flat top hill), the cemeteries expanding around them, as well as the ancient pier that is partially visible to this day. This area that is today's Kodra ex-military camp has been investigated throughout the 20th century, with the French, British and Russian troops of WWI conducting the first excavations in the cemeteries, while Prof. Konstantinos Romeos was the first to excavate the *toumba* settlement in 1930. A few excavational surveys have also been made by the 16th Ephorate of Prehistoric and Classic Antiquities on the *trapeza* of the site.⁸ The systematic excavation of the *toumba* settlement which has been going on since 1994, is the most extensive one and has brought to light a great number of both immovable structures (architectural structures, pits, walls) as well as movable objects (pottery, stone and metal finds, jewelry etc.) and modern day finds (military helmets, tools etc.).⁹ Archaeological finds aside, the diachronic phases of the excavation have also resulted in a multitude of methods and means of documentation, from analogue (maps, paper catalogues, photographs and drawings of finds), to 'semi-analogue' (e.g. scanned documents), to fully digital (databases, 3D models etc.). This diversity in documentation presented a challenge for its management and good use, in order to explore and cross-connect all the excavational data.

At Karabournaki, GIS primarily served as an organizational tool for efficient data handling, greatly enhancing the management of materials, notably the abundant ceramic artifacts.¹⁰ Starting in 2002,¹¹ the efforts have been channeled into the development of a geospatial platform, designed and implemented using various GIS software solutions.¹² Ultimately, the GIS platform found its cornerstone in custom versions of QGIS, a versatile open-source GIS software renowned for its comprehensive suite of tools for spatial data management, analysis, and visualization (Figure 1). From the inception of the project, the primary objective was to craft a digital dataset encompassing diverse layers of .shp files along with essential metadata, forming a well-rounded and organized repository. The overarching aim has been to establish a system that streamlines and accelerates

³ Hasenstab 1983; Lock 2003.

⁴ Kvamme 1999; Verhagen 2007; McCoy and Ladefoged 2009.

⁵ Verhagen 2018: 11–13.

⁶ Neubauer 2004; Orengo 2015.

⁷ Tiverios 2008: 8–31; 2009; Tsiafaki 2021.

⁸ Pantermali and Trakosopoulou 1998.

⁹ Tsiafaki and Manakidou 2021; Manakidou, Tiverios, and Tsiafaki 2022.

¹⁰ Tsiafaki *et al.* 2006.

¹¹ Tsiafaki 2005.

¹² On the process, see Huvila *et al.* 2018.

Figure 1. Architectural features in Karabournaki mapped using GIS overlaid on an orthophoto (KLEPSYDRA Cultural Inventory Digitization laboratory) of the site.

the process of data recording, integrating both vector and raster data sources seamlessly. By doing so, a dynamic environment has been created that eases the complexities of working with data at multiple scales, offering an indispensable asset during excavation periods. This system has not only fostered efficiency but has also significantly enhanced the ability to expedite mapping and reporting, which is a pivotal aspect of archaeological endeavors.

The methodology behind the design of the GIS project entailed a series of crucial decisions that fundamentally shaped how the archaeological data would be collected, organized, and represented within the GIS framework.¹³ These ontological decisions were pivotal, encompassing considerations such as which data elements to incorporate and the scale at which they would be portrayed. Equally important were choices like selecting the most suitable coordinate reference system (CRS), establishing rigorous data standards, and determining the optimal software and hardware infrastructure.

It quickly became evident, through a process of trial and error, that the accuracy and precision of these ontological decisions at the design stage were paramount to the project's overall success. This is the juncture where the logical and physical structure of the project platform must be meticulously crafted to accommodate the inherent constraints of the electronic format. Making informed and astute choices during this phase lays the foundation for a GIS system that not only

¹³ Peuquet 2002; Sun *et al.* 2019.

Figure 2. Architectural remains and distribution of pottery in Karabournaki.

harmonizes with the unique characteristics of the archaeological data but also sets the stage for a successful and efficient project implementation.

The integration of various methods into the data interpretation process yielded notable enhancements in terms of accuracy, efficiency, and speed. All permanent architectural remains were mapped and correlations with other archaeological findings were established within the GIS environment (Figure 2). This technological framework enabled the capturing, storing, and visual representation of spatial data, thus allowing intricate patterns and relationships to be discerned that might elude detection when analyzing non-spatial data in isolation.

The culmination of the efforts materialized in the form of a comprehensive digital map of the excavation site, a tapestry that highlighted the precise locations of architectural features such as walls, floors, and pits. By juxtaposing this spatial information with non-spatial data pertaining to artifact types and dating, a nuanced understanding of the intricate interplay between architectural features and various facets of the archaeological site began to emerge. This, in turn, allowed patterns of use and activity to be unearthed, shedding light on the dynamics within both open and enclosed spaces.

The utilization of layers was instrumental in the orderly organization of intricate data, affording the ability to present information visually in different ways, each tailored to varying scales and levels of detail. Through the thematic grouping of excavated elements by time period or feature type, specific findings and features were isolated and presented individually. This approach greatly simplified the process of identifying individual components within the intricate and visually interwoven landscape of archaeological objects.

Simultaneously, spatial queries were conducted to uncover correlations and connections among distinct categories of materials, which could serve as potential indicators of the presence of functional areas within the archaeological site. Through the amalgamation of spatial and non-spatial data and the execution of GIS queries – such as the identification of clusters of artifacts or features situated in close proximity to one another – a more comprehensive understanding of the excavation site was successfully obtained. This, in turn, facilitated insights into the behaviors and activities of the people who once inhabited it. By gradually discerning the specific areas used for various purposes, such as storing, living, or social gathering, a clearer understanding of the site's functional layout was provided. For example, clusters of storage vessels (pithoi) and remnants of other kinds of commercial vases were identified, potentially indicating dedicated storage areas, while concentrations of good quality imported pottery pinpointed habitation zones. Additionally, open spaces with evidence of communal activities, such as the large cobbled floor surfaces that have been found in different areas of the site, suggested open areas which may have been designated for social gatherings. These insights not only shed light on the daily lives and social structures of the inhabitants of this important trading hub but also enhanced the overall narrative of the archaeological site, providing a more nuanced and detailed reconstruction of human activities in the site.

However, the example of Karabournaki, when observed within its broader digital map context, highlights another valuable aspect of GIS for archaeologists: the ability to transition within the same project from analyzing individual sites to conducting broader-scale investigations.¹⁴ By providing the means to view and analyze data on a larger scale, GIS facilitates the identification of patterns and relationships that might prove challenging to discern through conventional methods. In the case of Karabournaki, encompassing its setting, visual relationships, and connections with other settlements across the Thermaic Gulf (covering at least 20 kilometers from Thessaloniki to the north to Aineia/Nea Michaniona to the south), this capability can allow archaeologists to manage a vast amount of information and approach the site holistically. This project is still underway, but this comprehensive perspective will, in the long term, enable a better understanding of the site's historical context and its interactions with neighboring settlements, facilitating more accurate reconstructions and interpretations of the ancient landscape and its usage.

Macroscale GIS. Exploring the fluvial landscapes of Aegean Thrace

Following this macroscale approach, AeGIS Athena investigated how the environment has influenced settlement patterns and ultimately the landscape in the extensive geographical area of Aegean Thrace, with a specific focus on the Delta of Nestos (an area covering approximately 320 square kilometers).¹⁵ Fluvial landscapes in the region are of particular interest because they consist of active and former river channels, off-channel water bodies, confluence environments, wetlands, floodplains, and riparian vegetation.¹⁶ The ancient sources like Pindar (Paeon II 1.25) point towards crop richness and agricultural wealth in the historical period, with the majority of these narratives speaking about a 'granary' which attracted early in the Archaic period Greek settlers from Asia Minor.¹⁷

The critical matter at hand revolves around ascertaining the extent to which the descriptions of the area's historical economy in ancient texts accurately reflect the reality of the past, and whether the ancient communities residing in the area would have perceived these descriptions similarly.¹⁸ This brings us to the pressing issue of broadening our understanding of the past beyond

¹⁴ On defining ranges of scale see Knappett 2011: 98; Knitter *et al.* 2018: 184–185 but also Knodell 2021: 19–23. See also the analysis in Kennedy this volume fn 29–33.

¹⁵ for the term, see Loukopoulou 2004.

¹⁶ Gerakis *et al.* 2007.

¹⁷ Isaac 1986: 75; Loukopoulou *et al.* 2005: 172; Tiverios 2008: 96; Kallintzi 2012.

¹⁸ Tsiafaki and Evangelidis 2021.

Figure 3. Classification of soils based on geological data in the area of Aegean Thrace. .

the confines of textual sources. To address this challenge, we embarked on an investigation into the productivity of the region from the perspective of historical ecology.¹⁹ This approach serves as a valuable tool in assessing settlement strategies and land management practices, all in response to the distinct ecological features—such as wetlands, soil characteristics, topography, and mineral resources—that have profoundly shaped the landscape of this region.²⁰

A fundamental aspect of the research involved the development of a GIS platform designed to facilitate the integration of diverse hydrological and geological data from various sources.²¹ These sources encompassed databases, as well as field test results, presented in a multitude of formats, including digital data and maps. The primary aim of this platform was to create a coherent and consistent structure that would enable the comprehensive analysis and visualization of environmental data and the results of field tests conducted in the region.²²

Within this framework, the platform was used to generate maps, conducting various spatial operations to assess soil productivity and the distribution of sites through customized queries. (Figure 3). Furthermore, we generated distinct distribution maps related to selected sites of interest, such as the Greek city of Abdera or its subsidiary city of Bergepolis (Figure 4). Bergepolis (possibly the modern area of Koutso)²³ appears to be a potentially significant site situated in the midst of an area rich in fertile soils, prompting the Abderitans to initiate a new period of colonization. This colonization effort may be attributed to a marked decline in the productivity of the alluvial lands near the city, as these wetland areas, which support hydrophytic vegetation, lack flood-intolerant

¹⁹ Sallares 1991; Grove and Rackham 2001; Blondel 2006.

²⁰ Egan and Howell 2001.

²¹ Tsiafaki and Evangelidis 2021.

²² Siart *et al.* 2018.

²³ Loukopoulou 2004: 877.

Figure 4. Assessment of soil productivity in the area of Abdera.

crops like cereals common in ancient farming, thereby supporting only low-intensity agriculture unsuitable for sustaining organized societies primarily dependent on farming.

The approach entailed the fusion of historical literature with a diverse array of information gleaned from systematic research spanning over a century in the region. Through the integration of the archaeological and geological data into a comprehensive GIS synthesis, we achieved a broader assessment of environmental attributes, thereby deepening our insights into specific terrains and the potential of geospatial technologies. The main goal was to create a complete environmental history of the area, focusing on how natural resources were used (and sometimes exploited), how landscapes changed, and the connections between human activities in the region. By doing this, the aim was to better understand how the interactions between people and their environment have influenced the area's history. In this context, it became evident that environmental variability and soil workability held significant sway in determining the settlement and economic strategies of the local Thracians and Greek colonists.²⁴ These findings gave rise to theories regarding the establishment of the Greek colonies (*apoikiai*) in the area suggesting regional and interregional transit trade as the main motivator opposed to agriculture which remains the dominant narrative in the area's archaeological interpretations.²⁵ Within this environment local communities exhibited unique land management practices, such as mixed farming, self-sustained animal husbandry, and seasonal habitation patterns, which further enriched our understanding of their historical dynamics.

Networks: the case of the sanctuary at Kalapodi

Network analysis²⁶ has emerged as a powerful tool for examining the connectivity and flow of goods. As models evolve to incorporate parameters such as distance, transportation costs, and

²⁴ Tsiafaki and Evangelidis 2021: 54–55.

²⁵ Donnellan 2016.

²⁶ Knappett 2013.

Figure 5. Network dataset from Kalapodi encompassing all the land, maritime routes, ports and shipwrecks.

other variables, the visualization and analysis of these flows offer a more nuanced understanding of trade and movement in antiquity.²⁷ An illustrative example of this is the study we conducted in collaboration with Dimitris Grigoropoulos (DAI) on the network of goods reaching the renowned sanctuary at Kalapodi in central Greece.²⁸ Within the context of D. Grigoropoulos' project²⁹ which applied social network theory to understand the dynamics behind the distribution of Roman pottery in the area, GIS techniques were used to create a network dataset (Figure 5) encompassing all the land and maritime routes and ports involved in the distribution of goods during the Roman period.

Ancient land routes were reconstructed through an analysis of historical and archaeological data, incorporating diverse sources such as archaeological surveys, historical maps, texts, and topographic information. The precise mapping of archaeological sites and geographical features was facilitated by various GIS resources available online.³⁰ In cases where data gaps were present, a method known as creating a cost surface³¹ was employed, with values assigned to terrain types based on their impact on travel. This allowed for the calculation of the least cost path³²

²⁷ Llobera 2000; Carroll and Carroll 2022.

²⁸ Grigoropoulos and Evangelidis 2023. We express our gratitude to Dr D. Grigoropoulos and Prof. K. Sporn (DAI) for generously providing us with access to the dataset from Kalapodi. The project is currently being prepared for a detailed publication, and this is just a brief note on the concept behind it.

²⁹ Grigoropoulos 2023. For social network analysis see Mills 2017.

³⁰ See for instance <https://projectmercury.eu/datasets/#roads> based on data from Barrington Atlas.

³¹ van Leusen 1999; Herzog 2013; Carroll and Carroll 2022; See also Antoniadis this volume.

³² Generally see White 2015; Surface-Evans and White 2012.

(as basically described by Langmuir and Tobler³³) between two points (for instance between the sanctuary of Kalapodi and different ancient harbors in the area), considering factors like distance and topography.

Subsequently, service area analysis within GIS³⁴ was employed to assess travel efficiency from major harbors to Kalapodi. Despite its limitations, this method proved to be a valuable tool for optimizing transportation networks and estimating travel times. Insights into ancient settlement patterns and trade networks were gained by examining maximum travel distances and evaluating accessibility. The analysis, which incorporated road networks and the results from the LCP, demonstrated Kalapodi's strategic role in connecting regions and aligning with ancient land routes, providing insights into historical trade and transportation dynamics.

In the course of the research, a thorough analysis of maritime trade routes and ports was conducted, constituting the second phase of the study. A network dataset was crafted in QGIS to identify the shortest routes between ports and consumption points, incorporating essential information on ports, maritime routes, and shipwrecks, while the reconstruction of sailing routes involved developing this dataset from charts and historical maps. Pascale Arnaud's³⁵ global route reconstruction served as a foundational reference, supplemented by contemporary sailing routes and charts, ensuring thorough coverage of the Aegean and Adriatic. Furthermore, shipwreck evidence was integrated with confirmed production areas and potential shipping points, such as Ephesus and Sinope (Figure 6). Valuable insights into navigation routes were gained from shipwrecks bearing cargo akin to Kalapodi's amphorae, enriching the comprehension of regional maritime trade patterns and potential goods movement.

Figure 6. Map highlighting potential trade routes in the area of Kalapodi.

³³ Langmuir 1984; Tobler 1993.

³⁴ For QGIS see https://docs.qgis.org/3.34/en/docs/user_manual/processing_algs/qgis/networkanalysis.html and for Esri <https://desktop.arcgis.com/en/arcmap/latest/extensions/network-analyst/service-area.htm>

³⁵ Arnaud 2005.

Using QGIS network tools, multiple vector based least cost path analyses were conducted on the network dataset, calculating the shortest routes on the water network. Focusing on Kalapodi as the endpoint and Mediterranean production centers as starting points, numerous maps highlighting potential trade routes were generated. Future research endeavors could further refine this analysis by incorporating wind patterns³⁶ and adapting the cost function to encompass wind speed and direction.³⁷

The initial assumption that strategic locations like Corinth and Chalkis (Figure 6) played pivotal roles in regulating the provincial supply chain, influencing the distribution of goods to Kalapodi, was reinforced by the model. Distinct routes for western and eastern imports were followed through the Corinthian Gulf and Euboean Gulf, respectively, enhancing the understanding of intricate trade dynamics within the region.³⁸ As demonstrated, network analysis serves not only to affirm existing knowledge but also to delve into alternative scenarios and unravel the complexities of Roman maritime trade. It offers a versatile tool for exploring diverse theories, not restricted to the shortest paths. For instance, the investigation of whether African pottery reached Kalapodi directly from Tripoli or via a route through Alexandria, Piraeus, and overland passages is possible through network analysis.

The results, compared with those from social network models, highlight the sanctuary's central role and the area's enhanced connectivity with different parts of the Roman world. By merging social network analysis with GIS network analysis, the aim is to develop a model that better understands the diverse aspects of travel and trade during the Roman period.

Visualizing the past: the contribution of game engines

While Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are crucial to archaeological research, they inherently possess structural limitations.³⁹ The prevalent spatial representations employed often present a rather monolithic view of landscape complexity.⁴⁰ Cartographic representations and point-based maps excel in modeling quantitative data, such as the dispersion of pottery. However, they fall short in capturing the nuanced qualitative aspects of human experience and practices, including movement, visibility, and the perception of landscapes.⁴¹

Dynamic spatial models can be effectively constructed by integrating real-time development platforms,⁴² like game engines, with Geographic Information System (GIS) data. The inclusion of gamification elements enables the exploration of dynamic features within a three-dimensional environment, addressing the challenges associated with comprehending such aspects through traditional two-dimensional maps.⁴³ Gamification techniques play a pivotal role in fostering active participation, engagement, and problem-solving skills.⁴⁴ In this context, we utilized Unity 3D to reconstruct and analyze several archaeological landscapes previously investigated through various GIS projects in AeGIS Lab over the years.

Unity 3D reconstructions, with their game-like attributes, offer an accessible and engaging yet cost-effective approach to representing archaeological data. Users can grasp complex concepts by actively participating in simulations, providing a tool to test the validity of archaeological

³⁶ McLean and Rubio – Campillio 2023.

³⁷ Jarriel 2018.

³⁸ Peeters 2023.

³⁹ Landeschi 2019.

⁴⁰ Llobera 2012.

⁴¹ Eve 2012.

⁴² Forte 2003.

⁴³ Lulof 2020.

⁴⁴ Brigham 2015; Seaborn and Fels 2015.

Figure 7. Reconstruction in Unity 3D of a coastal settlement (inspired by GIS data from Karabournaki).

assumptions about past human behaviors.⁴⁵ Moreover, Unity 3D simulations transform the exploration of landscapes into an ‘open environment’, moving beyond static representations. This facilitates the examination of intricate, multiscalar, and multivariate archaeological scenarios, transcending existing conceptual hypotheses.⁴⁶ Notably, elaborate multi-view 3D reconstructions are dispensable, and even low-polygon models of environmental and cultural features can effectively illustrate what Epstein terms ‘emergence’.⁴⁷

In the Unity 3D reconstruction process, GIS data are imported into the software, forming the foundation for crafting a detailed and precise virtual environment. Each model relies on a meticulous selection of information sources to generate virtual terrains, including elevation data, heightmaps, architectural drawings, 3D models, and outcomes from viewshed analyses. The quest for these data sources involves drawing from the wealth of information accumulated over previous years through diverse archaeological projects.⁴⁸

Leveraging Unity 3D, real-time exploration of movement, landscape perception, built environment density, proximity, and the physical volume perception of buildings was conducted by our team. This comprehensive investigation spanned diverse sites, ranging from expansive locales like the Nestos River delta to intricate micro-scapes, exemplified by the Egnatia road weaving through the villages of Xanthi. Taking inspiration from cases like Karabournaki (Figure 7), visibility was considered a strategic instrument for revealing settlement relationships and understanding the strategies employed to access and oversee crucial resources and spaces. This method holds substantial promise for examining relationships between individual actions or viewsheds. Through the utilization of Unity 3D, the capacity to craft visualizations of archaeological data, encompassing settlement patterns and micro-landscape reconstructions, is achieved. These visualizations serve as effective tools to aid users in grasping intricate datasets and discerning patterns within the archaeological landscape.

⁴⁵ Riva *et al.* 2004.

⁴⁶ On archaeological simulation see Whitley 2016.

⁴⁷ Epstein 1999; 2006.

⁴⁸ Evangelidis and Tsiafaki 2024.

Epilogue: a personal perspective

Despite the widespread use of GIS in archaeological practice, the archaeological community in Greece has not yet fully come to terms with the idea of this technology as an integral part of archaeological education. To a lot of archaeologists, the GIS tools have an auxiliary role which to a certain degree can aid the organization of data, but at the same time are limited to that role and cannot further enhance more complicated concepts of archaeological research and analysis. As a result, 'Archaeological GIS' continues to be a specialized field of expertise (often by people unrelated to academic and field archeology) and the development and dissemination of digital tools for specific archaeological purposes is often considered of secondary importance.⁴⁹

For us the experience we have gained through the work and organization of the Lab with geospatial software, geospatial platforms, and specialized tools like Unity 3D has highlighted the empowering opportunity to actively engage in modeling and experimenting with various archaeological hypotheses. This active involvement allows for the independent shaping of an analytical framework, reducing reliance on technologists to translate archaeological interests and questions into the digital realm. This shift has been facilitated not only by the growing computing capabilities of home computers but also by the increasing familiarity of (especially young) archaeologists with digital technology⁵⁰. As internet connectivity continues to improve, geospatial researchers are extending beyond the confines of their projects, enabling better sharing of data, results, and methods with the broader academic community, including non-experts.⁵¹ As a result, experience with GIS systems, especially open-source GIS, will continue to expand, and their use will become more widespread in the archaeological community. Archaeologists now recognize the importance of individuals within the discipline capable not only of entering data into such platforms but also of validating and analyzing the outcomes.⁵² Consequently, the time is ripe for a more systematic approach to integrating GIS into archaeological training and education. In such a system, students at all levels should acquire the skills to produce and utilize geospatial data for various projects related to their courses, research, or field archaeology. Crafting of course a GIS curriculum tailored for archaeologists demands meticulous planning, considering factors such as defining learning objectives, selecting suitable software, creating course materials, and providing hands-on training. Such a curriculum should provide a robust foundation in GIS theory and practice and be designed to meet the specific needs and objectives of archaeologists. Standardization of learning objectives, course content, course material and assessment methods will facilitate consistency across educational institutions, allowing for the development of a shared knowledge base and skill set within the archaeological community. However, the depth of this discussion exceeds the scope of a paper like this, suggesting the potential need for a future meeting to thoroughly explore the integration of GIS into archaeological training.

References

- Arnaud, P. 2005. *Les Routes de la navigation antique. Itinéraires en Méditerranée et mer Noire*. Paris: Errance.
- Blondel, J. 2006. The 'design' of Mediterranean landscapes: A millennial story of humans and ecological systems during the historic period. *Human Ecology* 34: 713–729.
- Brigham, T.J. 2015. An introduction to gamification: adding game elements for engagement. *Medical Reference Services Quarterly* 34: 471–480. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02763869.2015.1082385>.
- Carroll, F. and Carroll, E. 2022. 'Budget travel in the Mediterranean: A methodology for reconstructing ancient journeys through Least Cost Networks'. *Journal of Computer Applications in Archaeology* 5.1: 35–56. <https://doi.org/10.5334/jcaa.88>.

⁴⁹ Zubrow 2006; see also the discussion on the need for contextualized use of spatial tools in the papers by Antoniadis and Kennedy in this volume.

⁵⁰ See the discussion in Loy *et al.* in this volume but also Malaperdas in this volume.

⁵¹ Mak 2014.

⁵² Huggett 2017.

- Donnellan, L. 2016. 'Greek colonisation' and Mediterranean networks: patterns of mobility and interaction at Pithekoussai. *Journal of Greek Archaeology* 1: 109–149.
- Egan, D. and E. Howell 2001. *The historical ecology handbook: a restoration's guide to reference ecosystems*. Washington: Island Press.
- Epstein, J.M. 1999. Agent-based computational models and generative social science. *Complexity* 4 (5): 41–60.
- Epstein, J.M. 2006. Agent-based computational models and generative social science, in J.M. Epstein (ed.) *Generative Social Science: Studies in agent-based computational modeling*: 41–60. Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-0526\(199905/06\)4:5%3C41::AID-CPLX9%3E3.0.CO;2-F](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-0526(199905/06)4:5%3C41::AID-CPLX9%3E3.0.CO;2-F).
- Eve, S. 2012. Augmenting phenomenology: using augmented reality to aid archaeological phenomenology in the landscape. *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 19.4: 582–600. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-012-9142-7>
- Evangelidis, V. and D. Tsiadaki 2024. From GIS to Game engines: case studies in archaeology from North Greece. *Athens University Review of Archaeology* 7: 85–97. ISSN 2623-3428. <http://dx.doi.org/10.26247/aura7.3>.
- Forte, M. 2003. Mindscape: Ecological thinking, cyber-anthropology and virtual archaeological landscapes, in M. Forte and P.M. Williams (eds) *The reconstruction of archaeological landscapes through digital technologies, Proceedings of the 1st Italy-United States Workshop, Boston, Massachusetts* (British Archaeological Reports International Series 1151): 95–108. Oxford: Archaeopress.
- Gerakis, P., S. Tsiouris and V. Tsiaoussi 2007. *Water regime and biota: proposed minimum values of lakes water level and of rivers discharge in Macedonia and Thrace, Greece*. Athens: The Goulandris Natural History Museum.
- Grigoropoulos, D. 2023. Coarse wares of the middle and late Roman period from the 2015–2017 DAI Excavations at the Sanctuary of Kalapodi, East Phokis, in V. Caminneci, E. Giannitrapani, M. Concetta Parello and M.S. Rizzo (eds) *LRCW6: Late Roman coarse wares, cooking wares and amphorae in the Mediterranean: Archaeology and Archaeometry* (Roman and Late Antique Mediterranean Pottery 19): 626–638. Oxford: Archaeopress.
- Grigoropoulos, D. and V. Evangelidis 2023. Modelling regional dynamics and Roman pottery supply using network analysis and GIS: the sanctuary of Kalapodi in central Greece as a case study, in *7th European Conference on Social Networks (EUSN 2023) Centre for Methodology and Statistics of Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ljubljana, 4-8 September 2023* (Session CfP: Networks in history and archaeology) <https://zenodo.org/records/10160144>.
- Grove A.T. and O. Rackham 2001. *The nature of Mediterranean Europe. An ecological history*. Yale University Press, New Haven.
- Hasenstab, R.J. 1983. *A preliminary cultural resource sensitivity analysis for flood control facilities construction in the Passaic river basin of New Jersey*. Marietta, GA: US Army Corps of Engineer.
- Herzog, I. 2013. Theory and practice of cost functions, in F. Contreras, M. Farjas and F. Melero (eds) *CAA 2010: Fusion of Cultures. Proceedings of the 38th Annual Conference on Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology* (British Archaeological Reports International Series 2494): 375–382. Oxford: Archaeopress.
- Huggett, J. 2017. The apparatus of digital archaeology. *Internet Archaeology* 44. <https://doi.org/10.11141/ia.44.7>
- Huvila, I., L. Börjesson, N. Dell'Unto, D. Löwenborg, B. Petersson and P. Stenborg 2018. Archaeological information work and the digital turn, in I. Huvila (ed.) *Archaeology and Archaeological Information in the Digital Society*: 142–157. London and New York: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315225272-8>.
- Jarriel, K. 2018. Across the surface of the sea: maritime interaction in the Cycladic early bronze age. *Journal of Mediterranean Archaeology* 31: 52–76. Isaac, B.H. 1986. *The Greek settlements in Thrace until the Macedonian Conquest*. Leiden: Brill.
- Kallintzi, K.S. 2011. Η χώρα των Αβδήρων: συμβολή στην αρχαιολογία και ιστορική τοπογραφία του νότιου τμήματος του νομού Ξάνθης. Unpublished PhD dissertation, University of Thessaly.
- Knappett, C. 2011. *An archaeology of interaction. Network perspectives on material culture and society*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Knappett, C. (ed.) 2013. *Network analysis in archaeology: new approaches to regional interaction*. Oxford online edition, Oxford Academic.
- Knitter, D., G. Günther, W.B. Hamer, T. Keßler, J. Seguin, I. Unkel, E. Weiberg, R. Duttmann and O. Nakoinz. 2019. Land use patterns and climate change – a modeled scenario of the Late Bronze Age in Southern Greece. *Environmental Research Letters* 14, 125003: 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ab5126>.
- Knodell, A.R. 2021. *Societies in transition in Early Greece. An archaeological history*. Oakland: University of California Press.
- Kvamme, K.L. 1999. Recent directions and developments in Geographical Information Systems. *Journal of Archaeological Research* 7.2:

- 153–201. <https://doi.org/10.32028/exnovo.v4i0.369>
- Landeschi, G. 2019. Rethinking GIS, three-dimensionality and space perception in archaeology. *World Archaeology* 51.1: 17–32. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00438243.2018.1463171>
- Langmuir, E. 1984. *Mountaincraft and leadership: a handbook for mountaineers and hillwalking leaders in the British Isles*. Edinburgh: Scottish Sports Council.
- Levy, T.E. and N.G. Smith 2007. On-site GIS digital archaeology: GIS-based excavation recording in Southern Jordan, in T.E. Levy, P.M.M. Daviau, R.W. Younker and M. Shaer (eds) *Crossing Jordan: North American contributions to the Archaeology of Jordan*: 47–58. London and Oakville, CT: Equinox Publishing Ltd.
- Llobera, M. 2000. Understanding movement: A pilot model towards the sociology of movement, in G. Lock (ed.) *Beyond the map: archaeology and spatial technologies*: 65–84. Amsterdam: IOS Press.
- Llobera, M. 2012. Life on a pixel: challenges in the development of digital methods within an ‘interpretive’ landscape archaeology framework. *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 19 (4): 495–509. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-012-9139-2>
- Lock, G.R. 2003. *Using computers in archaeology: towards virtual pasts*. London: Routledge.
- Loukopoulou, L. 2004. Thrace from Nestos to Hebros, in M.H. Hansen and T.H. Nielsen (eds) *An inventory of Archaic and Classical Poleis*: 870–894. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Loukopoulou, L.D., M.G. Parissaki, S. Psoma and A. Zournatzi 2005. *Inscriptiones antiquae partis Thraciae quae ad ora maris Aegaei sita est (Praefecturae Xanthes, Rhodopes et Hebri). Ediderunt et commentariis sermone graeco conscriptis instruxerunt*. Athens: Research Centre for Greek and Roman Antiquity, National Hellenic Research Foundation.
- Lulof, P.S. 2020. Recreating reconstructions: Archaeology, architecture and 3D Technologies, in S. Dupré, A. Harris, J. Kursell, P. Lulof and M. Stols-Witlox (eds) *Reconstruction, replication and re-enactment in the humanities and social sciences*: 253–274. Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press <https://doi.org/10.1515/9789048543854-01>.
- Mak, B. 2014. Archaeology of a digitization. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology* 65: 1515–1526. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ASI.23061>
- Manakidou, E., M. Tiverios and D. Tsifaki 2022. 23 Χρόνια Πανεπιστημιακών Αρχαιολογικών ερευνών στο Καραμπουρνάκι. *Archaiologiko Ergo ste Makedonia kai Thrake* 30: 291–300.
- McCoy, M.D. and T.N. Ladefoged 2009. New developments in the use of spatial technology in archaeology. *Journal of Archaeological Research* 17: 263–295
- McLean, A. and Rubio-Campillo, X. 2022. Beyond least cost paths: circuit theory, maritime mobility and patterns of urbanism in the Roman Adriatic. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 138: 105534
- Mills, B. 2017. Social Network Analysis in Archaeology. *Annual Review of Anthropology* 46: 379–397. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-anthro-102116-041423>.
- Neubauer, W. 2004. GIS in Archaeology—The interface between prospection and excavation. *Archaeological Prospection* 11(3): 159–166.
- Orengo, H.A. 2015. Open Source GIS and geospatial software in archaeology: towards their integration into everyday archaeological practice, in A.T. Wilson and B. Edwards (eds) *Open Source Archaeology ethics and practice*: 64–82. Leiden: De Gruyter. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1515/9783110440171-006>.
- Pantermali, E. and E. Trakosopoulou 1998. Καραμπουρνάκι 1994. Η ανασκαφή της ΙΣΤ’ ΕΠΚΑ. *Archaiologiko Ergo ste Makedonia kai Thrake* 8: 203–215.
- Peeters, D. 2023. *Shaping regionality in socioeconomic systems*. Oxford: Archaeopress.
- Peuquet, D.J. 2002. *Representations of Space and Time*. New York: NY. Guilford Press.
- Riva, G., J. Waterworth and W. Eva 2004. The Layers of presence: a biocultural approach to understanding presence in natural and mediated environments. *Cyber Psychology and Behaviour* 7.4: 405–419. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1089/cpb.2004.7.402>.
- Sallares, R. 1991. *The Ecology of the Ancient Greek World*. London: Duckworth.
- Seaborn, K. and D. Fels 2015. Gamification in theory and action: A survey. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies* 74: 14–31.
- Siart, C., Forbriger, M. and O. Bubenzer 2018. Digital Geoarchaeology: bridging the gap between archaeology, geosciences and computer sciences, in C. Siart, M. Forbriger and O. Bubenzer (eds) *Digital Geoarchaeology. Natural Science in Archaeology*: 1–7. Springer: Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-25316-9_1.
- Sun, K., Y. Zhu, Y. P. Pan, Z. Hou, D. Wang, W. Li and J. Song 2019. Geospatial data ontology: the semantic foundation of geospatial data integration and sharing. *Big Earth Data* 3.3: 269–296.

- Surface-Evans, S.L. and D.A. White 2012. An introduction to the least cost analysis of social landscapes, in D.A. White and S.L. Surface-Evans (eds) *Least cost analysis of social landscapes: Archaeological case studies*: 1–10. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press.
- Tiverios, M. 2008. Greek Colonization of the Northern Aegean, in G.R. Tsetschkladze (ed.) *Greek Colonisation. An account of Greek colonies and other settlements overseas, vol. II*: 1–154. Leiden, Boston: Brill.
- Tiverios, M. 2009. Η πανεπιστημιακή ανασκαφή στο Καραμπουρνάκι Θεσσαλονίκης, in P. Adam-Veleni and K. Tsakalou-Tzanavari (eds) *Archaiologiko Ergo ste Makedonia kai Thrake 20 years*: 385–396. Thessaloniki: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki.
- Tobler, W. 1993. *Three presentations on geographical analysis and modeling. Non-Isotropic Modeling, Speculations on the Geometry of Geography, Global Geographical Analysis (93-1)*. Santa Barbara, CA: National Center for Geographic Information and Analysis, UC Santa Barbara. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.29268/stsc.2014.2.4.1>.
- Tsiafaki, D. 2005. Καραμπουρνάκι 2003: Εφαρμογές της σύγχρονης τεχνολογίας στις ανασκαφικές έρευνες του αρχαίου οικισμού. *Archaiologiko Ergo ste Makedonia kai Thrake* 17: 205–212.
- Tsiafaki, D. 2020. The Northern Aegean, in F. De Angelis (ed.) *A companion to Greeks across the ancient world*: 409–430. Wiley-Blackwell.
- Tsiafaki, D. 2021. Regional economies and productions in the area of the Thermaic Gulf, in M. Gleba, B. Marín-Aguilera and B. Dimova (eds) *Making cities. Economies of production and urbanization in Mediterranean Europe, 1000–500 BC*: 21–38. Cambridge: McDonald Institute for Archaeological Research.
- Tsiafaki, D. and E. Manakidou 2021. Ο οικισμός στο Καραμπουρνάκι, in A. Lioutas and Y. Karliambas (eds) *Κώμες και πολίσματα στον μυθό του Θερμαϊκού κόλπου*: 61–68. Greek Ministry of Culture & Ephorate of Antiquities of Thessaloniki City.
- Tsiafaki, D. and V. Evangelidis 2006. GIS as an interpretative tool in Greek archaeological research, in G. Priestnall and P. Aplin (eds) *Proceedings of the GIS Research UK 14th Annual Conference, GISRUK2006, 5th-7th April, 2006, Hosted by the School of Geography, The University of Nottingham*: 328–333. Nottingham, UK: The University of Nottingham.
- Tsiafaki, D. and V. Evangelidis 2021. Exploring rivers and ancient settlement in Aegean Thrace through spatial technology, in E. Kefalidou (ed.) *The riverlands of Aegean Thrace: production, consumption and exploitation of the natural and cultural landscapes. River valleys and regional economies: Panel 2.4 | Panel 2.7, Archaeology and Economy in the Ancient World 6*: 45–61. Heidelberg: Propylaeum. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.11588/propylaeum.871.c11424>.
- Tsiafaki, D., A. Tsompanopoulos, G. Pavlidis, N. Tsirliganis, V. Evangelidis, and Ch. Chamzas 2006. Archiving cultural objects in the 21st century: pottery from Karabournaki, in C.C. Mattusch, A.A. Donohue and A. Brauer (eds) *Common ground: archaeology, art, science, and humanities, Proceedings of the XVI International Congress of Classical Archaeology*: 419–23. Oxford: Oxbow Books.
- Tsionas, I., D. Tsiafaki, N. Tsirliganis and V. Tsioukas 2009. 3D GIS for the archeological excavation at Karabournaki, Thessaloniki, in *Proceedings of the International workshop 'Spatial Information for Sustainable Management of Urban Areas', Mainz, Germany, 2-4/2/2009*. FIG Commission 3. Available at <http://ikee.lib.auth.gr/record/212215>.
- van Leusen, P. 1999. Viewshed and cost surface analysis using GIS (Cartographic modelling in a cell-based GIS II), in J. Barcelo, I. Briz and A. Villa (ed.) *New techniques for old times-computer applications and quantitative methods in archaeology: Proceedings of the 26th Conference, Barcelona, 1998* (British Archaeological Reports International Series 757): 215–223. Oxford
- Verhagen, P. 2007. *Case studies in archaeological predictive modelling*. Leiden: Leiden University Press
- Verhagen, P. 2018. Spatial analysis in archaeology. Moving into new territories, in C. Siart, M. Forbriger and O. Bubbenzer (eds) *Digital geoarchaeology. Natural science in archaeology*: 11–25. Springer: Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-25316-9_2.
- Wheatley, D. and M. Gillings 2003. *Spatial technology and archaeology: the archaeological applications of GIS*. London: Taylor & Francis.
- White, D.A. 2015. The basics of least cost analysis for archaeological applications. *Advances in Archaeological Practice* 3.4: 407–414.
- Whitley, T.G. 2016. Archaeological simulation and the testing paradigm, in M. Brouwer Burg, J.H.M. Peeters and W. Lovis (eds) *Uncertainty and sensitivity analysis in archaeological computational modeling*: 131–156. Switzerland: Springer International Publishing.
- Zubrow, E. 2006. Digital archaeology: the historical context, in T. Evans and P. Daly (eds) *Digital archaeology: bridging method and theory*: 10–31. London and New York: Routledge.